

Over the Air Computation for Distributed Power Control using SDR Testbed

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Abstract—Interference management is a critical challenge in future wireless networks, requiring scalable solutions beyond centralized approaches. In this work, we propose and experimentally validate an over-the-air computation framework for distributed power control on a Software-Defined Radio (SDR) testbed. Using the graph neural networks (GNNs) paradigm, our approach embeds message-passing operations within standard 3GPP Synchronization Signal Blocks (SSBs) to efficiently exchange Neural Network Information (NNI) along with known channel state information (CSI). By aggregating signals directly in the wireless medium, the communication overhead related to message passing is reduced, while the inherent synchronization capabilities of SSBs ensure precise timing and coordination. Experimental results show that the resulting power-control policy delivers throughput gains, underscoring its practical utility for 6G networks and subnetworks.

Index Terms—Over the air computation; distributed power control; interference management; software defined radio.

I. INTRODUCTION

Next-generation wireless systems come with more demanding requirements on reliability, latency, and scalability, making interference management one of the most critical design objectives [1]. As networks grow denser, effective radio resource management challenges traditional centralized schemes. These solutions often require extensive coordination and extra overhead between the network and devices, becoming impractical for large-scale deployments [2].

These challenges have shifted interest to distributed interference-management strategies that allow devices to autonomously adjust transmission parameters based on local observations [3]. Simultaneously, AI and Machine Learning (ML)-based approaches are favored for their ability to better capture interference patterns along with complex dynamics of wireless channels [4]. Among those data-driven techniques, Graph Neural Networks (GNNs) including their subcategories such as message-passing—can facilitate local information exchange and collaborative decision-making [5], [6].

However, two key challenges remain. Firstly, while algorithmic advancements are progressing rapidly, their practical validation under real-world conditions is still limited. Secondly, AI/ML models typically require frequent exchanges of parameters (e.g., weights and gradients), which can impose a significant communication burden on the network. Over-the-air computation has emerged as a promising solution to address this overhead [7]. By exploiting the broadcast nature of the wireless medium, it enables simultaneous aggregation

of transmitted signals directly in the air, thereby reducing latency and the need for explicit data exchange needed [8].

To bridge the gap from practical implementation, Software-Defined Radio (SDR) platforms have emerged as critical enablers of prototyping in realistic conditions [9]. Testbeds based on them have been used to deploy both traditional [10], as well as AI-driven interference mitigation strategies [11]. Furthermore, SDRs have also been utilized to prototype Over-the-Air Computation, enabling real-world validation of its efficiency [12]. Alongside those hardware solutions, open source software frameworks Open5GS, which provides a modular 3GPP core network, and srsRAN, offering flexible base station and user equipment stacks, pave the way for rapid development of advanced end-to-end cellular systems [13]. By harnessing these tools, researchers can build proof-of-concept (PoC) testbeds that maintain standards compliance under practical radio conditions [14].

In this paper, we present a working proof of concept for over-the-air distributed power control within the 6G-SHINE project [15]. Leveraging Air-MPRNN principles from recent theoretical work [16], we embed the message passing into standard 3GPP Synchronization Signal Blocks (SSBs) rather than using custom pilots, for example Channel State Information Reference Signal (CSI-RS). This choice is driven by the synchronization requirements of real-world SDR deployments and the need for coherent signal aggregation, as dictated by Over-the-Air computation. The resulting testbed shows how the learned power-control policy can significantly boost throughput for future 6G networks and subnetworks.

The remainder of this paper is organized as follows. Section II outlines the system model for our 6G subnetworks. Section III details the over-the-air computation framework, including our choice to use SSB-based message passing. Section IV describes the setup of the SDR testbed and presents experimental findings, while Section V concludes the paper and identifies future research directions.

II. SYSTEM MODEL

In 6G, subnetworks are envisioned as localized communication environments operating within a larger network infrastructure. They are designed to meet demanding communication requirements, such as ultra-low latency and high throughput, often in complex environments like industrial settings, vehicles, and even within the human body [15]. At the core of these subnetworks are High Capability (HC)

nodes, Low Capability (LC) nodes, and Subnetwork Elements (SNEs). HC nodes function as primary units with advanced networking and computational capabilities, serving as central hubs that manage subnetwork operations and ensure coordination with the larger 6G framework. LCs are nodes with reduced capabilities and assist HCs by handling specific localized tasks. SNEs represent highly constrained devices, such as sensors or actuators, that contribute to the network's overall functionality. Together, these components form a flexible and scalable architecture.

Due to the subnetworks' dynamic and dense nature, they often operate within shared frequency bands, making interference management a critical design consideration. While the broader 6G network can offer a centralized solution, it is highly advantageous for subnetworks to implement distributed interference management methods. This independence enhances their adaptability to local conditions while reducing reliance on the 6G network, which is particularly beneficial in scenarios with limited connectivity. For HC nodes to support this, they are equipped with Radio Resource Management (RRM) functionality, dynamically allocate resources, and apply power control within the subnetwork. The policy of how the RRM makes decisions can be static, utilizing an optimization function, or dynamic, utilizing AI/ML techniques. For the latter, to enable a distributed computation, Neural Network Information (NNI) between the subnetworks needs to be exchanged. An overall architecture with two subnetworks is illustrated in Figure 1.

III. OVER THE AIR COMPUTATION FOR DISTRIBUTED POWER CONTROL

Typically, the HC nodes periodically broadcast a set of reference signals to allow SNEs to detect them for initiating attachment procedures and be in sync with them. In 5G, this set of signals is SSB [17]. This block contains the Primary and Secondary Synchronization Signal (PSS and SSS) and the Physical Broadcast Channel (PBCH). The role of Synchronization Signals (SSs) is for over-the-air radio frame synchronization without the need for additional time and frequency synchronization devices. They are placed in a specific position within a frame, with the PSS detected first and the SSS after. The PBCH carries the Master Information Block (MIB), which contains information related to reference signals subcarrier spacing and position in the resource grid. We utilize these broadcasted signals to exchange the NNI between the subnetworks in our system model. Assuming that HC nodes utilize SSB, we allow interference-free information passing with a predefined scheduling broadcast. That said, in the case of a network with two subnetworks, one HC node broadcasts the SSB at the beginning of a radio frame, and the other HC broadcasts at the half frame, as illustrated in Figure 2.

The key principle for this model to work is that while one HC broadcasts SSB, the other one keeps the resources free to avoid unintentional interference. The result of this mechanism is an overhead as the resource grid is reserved for the multiple SSBs broadcasting. The overhead can be

minimized by broadcasting the SSBs on the same Resource Blocks (RBs) but on different radio frames, increasing the latency of the NNI exchange. On the other hand, we could avoid any overhead by utilizing a reference signal scheduled at specific RBs and broadcasted simultaneously from all HC nodes. However, such a solution requires additional hardware for high-precision frequency and time synchronization and a sophisticated signal generation design, e.g., with orthogonal sequences.

To implement a specific RRM solution, a distributed power control mechanism for interference management has been developed using the Air Message Passing Recurrent Neural Network (Air-MPRNN) paradigm, as introduced in [16]. This approach is based on a Message Passing Neural Network (MPNN) built on a GNN, which has been theoretically demonstrated to enable efficient distributed power control. In this work, a practical implementation within a 3GPP-based subnetwork is presented to illustrate how over-the-air neural network computation can be effectively deployed in real-world scenarios. The MPNN framework is scalable with the number of vertices, where each vertex represents a 6G subnetwork, and the edges denote direct and interference links within and between subnetworks. The distributed power control method leverages the temporal correlation of wireless channels, making the wireless network recursive and reducing the time required for network output generation. Each MPNN model follows a sequence of steps detailed as follows. The process begins with a message generation phase, where each vertex transmits a message to its neighboring vertices. This is followed by a message aggregation phase, in which each vertex collects messages from its neighbors. Subsequently, each vertex updates its state and generates an output before the cycle repeats.

The MPNN's vertices, embedded within the HC nodes, execute these steps as follows. A Multi-Layer Perceptron (MLP) model handles message generation, taking as input the vertex embeddings, which store the internal state of each vertex. This is followed by the message passing phase, where messages are represented as pilot transmit power, regulating the HC's SSB transmission power. Each SNE can receive messages from all HC nodes through SSB measurements. Once the SNEs extract the messages, they report them back to their serving HC node. Another MLP model then updates the vertex's internal state using the received messages as input. This updated state is recursively fed back into the message-generation MLP for the next iteration of the framework. Finally, a third MLP model computes the NN's output by processing the vertex's internal state. This output determines the power control for data transmission from HC nodes to SNEs, ensuring that the transmit power is optimized to minimize interference between subnetworks.

Figure 3 illustrates two HC/SNE pairs utilizing MPNN to regulate downlink transmit power in a distributed manner, enabling collective power control decisions to maximize the overall network's sum rate. Each HC node integrates an AI/ML model that functions as an MPNN vertex. Power control occurs in the downlink direction, facilitating message

Fig. 1: AI/ML-based RRM architecture for 6G subnetworks.

Fig. 2: Radio frame with two scheduled SSBs on different slots of the resource grid for different HCs.

passing and interference management. Each SNE receives signals from its serving HC node, combined with interference from other HCs and Gaussian noise. The results of channel estimation are fed back to the HC node via the uplink channel. A centralized manager, hosted at the 6G base station, synchronizes the MPNN vertices to work in a coordinated manner. Although the figure depicts only two HC/SNE pairs, the implementation is scalable to accommodate any number of pairs. Additional HC nodes connect to the 6G parent network, and their corresponding SNEs receive the downlink signal alongside interference and noise from other HCs.

Fig. 3: Distributed power control through MPNN for interference management in 6G subnetworks.

IV. EXPERIMENTAL SETUP AND RESULTS

A. Experimental Set up

We deployed the proposed solution in a functional environment using the Open5GS and srsRAN software suites alongside USRP SDR hardware. Open5GS is an open-source core network implementation designed for constructing and managing NR/LTE mobile networks, [18]. Similarly, srsRAN is an open-source platform that allows researchers, developers, and telecom professionals to implement and experiment with LTE and 5G protocols using SDRs or a fully software-based setup, [19]. It offers a flexible framework for developing, testing, and deploying cellular network technologies, making it a valuable asset for wireless communication research. Its modular architecture and extensive documentation ensure

accessibility for both academic and industry users. Ettus Research, a National Instruments (NI) brand, is a prominent provider of SDR hardware and solutions. Best known for its USRP product line, Ettus Research supports researchers, engineers, and developers in prototyping and deploying wireless communication systems, with applications ranging from spectrum analysis to signal processing and 5G research [20].

For our experiments, we utilized four B210 SDR devices forming two subnetworks. Each subnetwork includes one gNB cell forming an HC node and one UE as an SNE. Figure 4 (b) displays the devices placed on a testbed and their respective roles. The gNBs were fixed on opposite sides, at around $1.5m$ distance, while the UEs were placed in the in-between space. Omnidirectional antennas of $15cm$ in length perform the downlink communication, while the uplink communication is through the white SMA cables. All SDR devices are attached to a high-performance desktop computer with an Intel Core i9 CPU and 32GB RAM using USB 3 cables. The left column of Table I shows the parameters influencing the RF channel conditions. The SDRs were configured to operate at $1.93GHz$ carrier frequency with $11.52MS/S$ sampling frequency. The transmission and reception gains were set at $58dB$ and $40dB$, respectively, to allow measurements in a wide range of SNR values in the $1.5m$ in-between space.

TABLE I: Wireless Communication Parameters

RF Parameter	Value	5G Parameter	Value
Carrier Band	$N2(1.93GHz)$	Bandwidth	$10MHz$
Sample Rate	$11.52MS/S$	SCS	$15KHz$
Antenna Length	$15cm$	Symbols/Slots	$14/10$
Tx/Rx Gain	$58dB/40dB$	Frame Period	$10ms$
Max Distance	$1.5m$	Cyclic Prefix	Normal

Appropriate wireless channels are generated for direct and cross-links to train in offline manner the proposed implementation under these conditions. Each generated channel reduces signal power due to path loss and multipath fading. For path loss calculations, the propagation model for ultra-high frequencies from [21] was used, which considers factors such as transmitter-receiver distance, antenna heights, and carrier wavelength. As the distance between the transmitter and receiver increases, path loss follows a logarithmic growth. In addition to path loss, multipath fading is simulated using a mathematical formula from [22], where the key variable is the channel correlation coefficient, determining how smoothly or abruptly the channel varies over time. Based on this coefficient, a circularly symmetric complex Gaussian distribution is computed, and a randomly sampled value from this distribution is added dynamically.

The neural network training dataset comprises 5000 layouts within a $1.5m \times 1.5m$ area, each containing two randomly placed transmitter-receiver pairs. During training, 80% of the dataset is used to update network weights, while the remaining 20% is reserved for validation at each epoch to prevent overfitting. The RF parameters used to compute channel conditions match those employed in the SDR devices. For

network architecture and training settings, including epoch count and optimizer selection, various hyperparameters were evaluated, and the optimal configuration was chosen based on performance. Table II presents these values, detailing the structures of the message generation MLP, the update MLP, and the output MLP. The batch size was 50 layouts, representing the number of random layouts per epoch used to adjust the MLP weights for optimizing the reward function, defined as the harmonic mean of each pair’s rate. The training was conducted on the desktop PC using the PyTorch library, [23].

TABLE II: Neural Network Hyper-parameters

Parameter	Value	Parameter	Value
Message MLP	{9, 32, 32, 1}	Batch size	50
Embedding MLP	{10, 32, 8}	Initial LR ^a	0.004
Output MLP	{8, 16, 1}	LR decay factor	0.9
Embedding size	8	LR decay step	10
Epochs	100	Optimizer	Adam [24]

^aLearning Rate.

Once the model achieved satisfactory performance in the simulated environment, we moved to the actual test case and evaluation. For this, the computer executes the gNBs and UEs, which are instances of the srsRAN software suite, and the Open5GS core network in a Docker environment. The 5G numerology parameters for the wireless communication between gNBs and UEs are displayed in Table I. It also handles all MPNN functions, including two vertices—one for each pair—and a centralized scheduler process. The scheduler communicates with all MPNN vertices and coordinates them to enable organized message-passing broadcasts. Coordination is crucial, as the vertices may operate at different execution speeds, but a power decision is only valid when all messages have been received and aggregated. Data exchange between processes is managed through interprocess communication using the ZeroMQ library, which supports multiple programming languages and provides a lightweight, flexible messaging layer that abstracts the complexities of socket programming, [25]. A general architecture of implementation with the processes is displayed in Figure 4 (a).

After each message generation phase, each MPNN vertice translates the message into the transmit power of the SSB. The gNBs broadcast their reference signal in alternate order, allowing the UEs to receive them without interference and perform channel estimation to extract the messages. With the received messages, the MPNN vertices update their internal state and calculate the output. According to that output, the gNBs configure the transmit power of the data signals. We create downlink data traffic by utilizing the iPerf3 tool, [26], and setting up servers on the UE side and clients on the core network. The clients are constantly sending packets at a desired throughput, and the servers are listening to those packets and calculating the network metrics.

B. Experimental Results

In this section, measurement results of the proposed PoC are presented and compared with the bare metal setup

Fig. 4: Experimental setup (a) as an illustration between the processes and SDR devices and (b) in an actual environment with the real SDRs.

where no power control is implemented for interference management. Fifteen setup scenarios were measured, each for different channel conditions of the two pairs. To set the desired channel condition, we observed the measured SNR reported from the UEs while slowly moving around each UE. To increase the SNR, we moved the UE closer to the serving gNB cell, and to decrease it, we moved it further away and closer to the interfering cell. The working range of SNRs was between $3dB$ and $15dB$.

Figure 5 illustrates the rates of each pair when power control for interference management is applied (GNN) and when both cells transmit equally with maximum power (Equal Power Allocation EPA). The desired behavior is that the pair with high throughput on EPA policy reduces its throughput on GNN policy by lowering its transmit power, allowing the link with low throughput on EPA to increase its throughput on GNN. Such a behavior is clearly displayed in scenarios 3 – 9, 3 – 12, 3 – 15, and 9 – 15. The performance gain when using GNN over EPA is better illustrated in Figure 6. Each element in the matrix shows the percentage improvement of the overall network’s harmonic mean of each pair’s throughput. The harmonic mean metric choice ensures fairness in the network as lower rates have more influence on the final measure.

These measurements result in the following outcomes. In general, as the SNR of each pair is increased, its throughput improves accordingly, as expected, whereas better channel conditions result in higher data rates. The more unequal the channel conditions between the two pairs are, the higher the overall performance gain. This is observed in the mentioned scenarios, where the improvement starts at 8.5% and maximizes at 41.5%. These results verify the correctness of our implementation, taking appropriate power control decisions to worsen the favored pair and improve the conditions of the unfavored. On the other hand, we expected scenarios

Fig. 5: Throughput as reported by each UE over different SNR combinations for each UE when applying GNN and EPA power control policy.

where the channel conditions are similar in both pairs, e.g., combinations 6 – 6, 9 – 9, 12 – 12, and 15 – 15, to be no performance improvement as the optimal power control policy is the EPA. However, our implementation performed worse in those cases, especially in high SNR combinations where the worst performance achieved $-24%$ gain. This negative outcome can originate from inefficient NN training.

V. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORK

In this paper, we presented a working PoC for the over-the-air distributed power control between subnetworks, which is based on the Air-MPRNN concept. Motivated by the tight synchronization demands of real SDR testbed, message passing was embedded to SSB signalling rather than some other 3GPP reference signal. This design choice is particularly important for standalone subnetworks that may

SNR2		3dB	6dB	9dB	12dB	15dB
SNR1	3dB	-1.18%	4.50%	10.30%	33.04%	41.53%
	6dB		-5.26%	3.24%	7.70%	33.26%
9dB				-5.51%	-8.11%	8.52%
12dB					-23.76%	2.35%
15dB						-19.18%

Fig. 6: Percent improvement of the network's harmonic mean throughput for different channel condition combination.

lack alternative synchronization channels from a parent 6G station. With an SDR-based set-up featuring USRP devices, Open5GS, and srsRAN, we demonstrated that GNN-driven interference management can boost throughput under uneven SNR conditions, achieving up to a 41.5% improvement over a system lacking power control. This confirms that a learned policy can effectively reallocate transmission power to weaker links, enhancing overall fairness. However, certain high-SNR or balanced-SNR cases exhibited negative gains, revealing potential limitations in the neural network training process. Moreover, while SSBs can simplify the synchronization process they must be carefully managed as they introduce an overhead–latency trade-off that intensifies with network scaling. As future work, we aim to refining training methods, including potentially over-the-air learning, and extending the system to multi-subnetwork scenarios. Overall, our implementation demonstrates a feasible path toward distributed, AI-driven RRM in next-generation networks.

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